

Pairwise comparisons for small samples from mixtures of normal distributions: the unexpected role of skewness

Mark E. Eakin and Mary M. Whiteside

Department of Information Systems and Operations Management, The University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX, United States

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Mary M. Whiteside, The University of Texas at Arlington, Box 19437, Arlington, TX 76019

Email: whiteside@uta.edu

Mark E. Eakin <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2603-5450>

Mary M. Whiteside <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4987-4580>

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Abstract

This paper simulates the performance of two pairwise comparison procedures when distributions are normal mixtures (sometimes exhibiting heteroscedasticity and/or skewness). The two procedures are Tukey's (1949) using the Hayter-Fisher (1986) adjustment (HFF) compared to a novel procedure we name EHF that adjusts for heteroscedasticity based on the methods of Brown-Forsythe (1974), Mehrotra (1997), and Games-Howell (1976). The heterogeneity adjustments of EHF provide the expected protection against Type I errors but with a loss of power. The HFF procedure is acceptably robust and more powerful than EHF in all cases. Tables present specific metrics for robustness and power comparing EHF to HFF for the case where the performance of the two procedures is most similar: small sample sizes, extreme heteroscedasticity, and maximized difference in skewness and kurtosis among the populations. For the design of this simulation, surprisingly, the direction of skewness (whether positive or negative) impacts the correlation of mean square treatment (MST) and mean square error (MSE), which is associated with the power of the procedures.

Keywords: ANOVA methods; power and robustness; computer simulation procedures; assumption violations

Introduction

Simultaneous procedures, such as all pairwise comparisons of means with or without an analysis of variance (ANOVA), have drawn the renewed attention of statisticians and other researchers in the era of genomics, observations from functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI's), and other applications with hundreds or even thousands of simultaneous procedures. Frequently,

however, especially in genomics and medical research, the number of simultaneous procedures has increased by orders of magnitude while the number of observations within groups may still be small. For example, Brad Efron, in the American Statistical Association presidential address August 2004 in Toronto (2005) describes a comparison of gene expressions for seven breast cancer tumors with BRCA1 mutations to eight breast cancer tumors with BRCA2 mutations at 3,226 genes (Hedenfalk, et al., 2001).

Moreover, in many of these applications of simultaneous procedures, the assumptions of normality and homogeneous variance are known to be violated. Non-normality and heterogeneity have been extensively studied, and it is well known that small samples magnify the effect of non-normality. But the specific effect of normal mixture distributions has not been studied in any comprehensive way. fMRI data provides an example of normal mixtures, in particular Pendse, Borsook, and Becerra show “theoretically as well as by simulation that for real fMRI data various factors lead to a mixture of Gaussian ... densities for the null distribution” (2009, p. 231). But a normal mixture may also result from a misspecification of the model. See the following references for a discussion of the role of outliers in identifying model misspecification (Jiao & Pretis, 2017; Doornik & Hendry, 2016; Johansen & Nielsen, 2016).

Our results are applicable to single factor experiments where there is an unrecognized normal mixture resulting from model misspecification. Consider for example an experiment where researchers attempt to replicate parts of the Wageman and Baker (1997) 3x3 factorial experiments on the effect of task interdependence and reward interdependence on team performance and cooperation in an education setting. Since a significant interaction effect on performance occurs between task and reward interdependence, let us assume that researchers choose four of the factor level combinations (High-High, High-Low, Low-High, and Low-Low)

for a subsequent completely randomized one-way experiment to see if differences are again significant for a new measure of performance. While Wageman and Baker (1997) created same sex pairs for teams, researchers now assign pairs randomly without regard to same sex pairing. However, unbeknownst to them, their new measure of performance is sensitive to the pairing of the sexes with female only pairing responding differently from mixed and male only pairs as described by Aries (1976). Suppose further the participants in the new experiment are selected from a population in which 16 out of every 17 pairs are male only or mixed, i.e., only one female only pair. The distribution of performance for the four combinations of pairings are displayed in Figure 1 for the population of all possible pairs. In Figure 1a, the large distributions are the performance for male only or mixed sex pairs while the smaller, sometimes indiscernible, distributions are for female only pairs. Figure 1b displays only the means of those eight subpopulations. Differences between the four-population means are small for the populations of pairs that have males in them, but there is a greater difference for female only pairs. However, when combining the experimental data, ignoring the sex makeup of the pairs (i.e., analyzing a normal mixture resulting from a model misspecification), the first three levels have zero effect, and the fourth level has only a slight positive effect. Note that using trimmed means will restrict the inferences to the subpopulations containing males. This example represents the case considered extensively herein as a normal mixture with extreme heterogeneity and one extreme mean.

[Insert Figure 1 here]

Results in Ramsey et al. (2011) motivate the primary objectives of this paper. In that work, the authors show that the readily available and frequently used ordinary F test followed by the Hayter-Fisher PCP (Hayter, 1986), referred to as HFF, is on average both reasonably

conservative with respect to Type I error and relatively powerful among procedures considered for normal, uniform, double exponential, and exponential distributions, with and without equal variance and outliers. Here we show that the performance of HFF is comparable for a variety of normal mixtures. We also define a new procedure, EHF, hoping to improve on HFF by adjusting for heterogeneity both the initial F test and the Hayter-Fisher PCP. Our simulation design examines the performance of HFF and EHF with and without an initial ANOVA when comparing groups with small sample sizes from normal mixtures. The selected design settings allow various values of the mixing ratio, differences in variance, and effect sizes. The simulation includes cases where distributions are negatively skewed as well as positively skewed. It turns out that the direction of skewness combined with the location of the one extreme mean (i. e. whether greater than or less than the other means) influences the relative performance of PCPs even when mixing ratios, variances, and effect sizes are unchanged. This seemingly surprising outcome results from the long known but rarely considered correlation of the numerator (mean square treatment, MST) and denominator (mean square error, MSE) of the ANOVA F test statistic when underlying distributions are skewed (Donaldson, 1968) . Delaney and Vargha (2000) study the impact of different magnitudes of skewness for the two-sample case with respect to robustness.

Literature review

PCPs date back at least as far as 1935 to Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) t test (1935). See also (Wilcox, 2017) . Other early and still frequently used procedures for making all pairwise comparisons are Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) (1949) adapted for unequal sample sizes by Kramer (1956), Newman-Keuls (Keuls, 1952; Newman 1939), Bonferroni (1936), Dunn, (1961), and Scheffe (1953). These procedures along with Fisher's

protected LSD, i.e., following a significant ANOVA, are designed to control family wide error rate (FWER), defined as the probability of at least one Type I error among all pairwise comparisons. Various modifications of these early procedures have been suggested to improve power and thereby decrease the probability of Type II error. These modifications include Hayter's, referred to as the Hayter-Fisher (1986), Peritz's (1970), and procedures designed to control the False Discovery Rate (FDR), defined as the average proportion of Type I errors given all significant differences, (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) rather than the more stringent criterion of controlling FWER. Most of these procedures are based on assumptions of equal variance and normality. Procedures developed specifically for analysis of variance and post hoc pairwise comparisons when variances are unequal include those of Brown and Forsythe (1974), Games and Howell (1976), Dunnett (1980), and Tamhane (1977, 1979). However, of the 573 publications from academic journals dealing with multiple comparison procedures that Rao and Swarupchand list in their 2009 bibliography (2009), only eight papers specifically consider the unequal variance case. The few papers listed in their bibliography that compare the performance of selected PCPs for non-normal and heterogeneous distributions find no generally best procedure with performance dependent upon the shape and parameters of the distributions.

Power can be increased by trimming outliers frequently associated with heterogeneity and non-normality (Wilcox, 2017). However, when distributions are normal mixtures with a small value of the mixing ratio, removing outliers will eliminate all or an extremely substantial portion of the information about a subpopulation hidden within the sampled data. This is still relevant information that the researcher needs (Bailey, 2018) and (Watson & Hand, 2014). Therefore, this study examines what happens when all outliers are retained. The traditional remedies for violation of the assumptions of normality and equal variance seem to differ by

custom in different disciplines. These remedies generally take one of the following approaches: nonparametric procedures designed specifically for non-normal distributions but requiring symmetry to test the hypothesis of equal means, e.g., the Wilcoxon two independent sample test (1945); procedures designed specifically for unequal variance but assuming normality, e.g., Brown-Forsythe ANOVA adjustments (1974) and Games-Howell pairwise comparisons (1976); transformation of the response variable, e.g., Box-Cox transformations (1964); the use of data driven procedures, e.g., trimmed means, bootstrapping, and Winsorizing (Wilcox, 2017); and Bayesian procedures such as FDR (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995) and empirical Bayes methods. Each of these approaches has obvious limitations for some metrics, in some instances, and for small samples which can exhibit simultaneously unequal variances and skewness, such as normal mixtures.

Since Rao and Swarupchand's bibliography (2009), additional researchers have turned their attention to the implications of simultaneous non-normality and heterogeneity for the relative performance of various ANOVA omnibus tests and PCPs. Papers by Ramsey et al. (2010, 2011), Fan and Hancock (2012), Parra-Frutos and Molera (2021), and Stehlik et al. (2024) address the need for a more comprehensive comparison of available procedures under the simultaneous violation of normality and equal variance assumptions. The Ramsey papers generally find once again that there is no one best procedure for all cases. However, the Peritz procedure with Brown-Forsythe tests, that Ramsey et al. (2011) investigate, is robust for the conditions simulated with no great power loss. Any-pair power, the proportion of runs where the procedure detected at least one true difference in means, is generally best with the Hayter-Fisher procedure following an overall F-test (HFF), which also exhibits relatively good all-pairs power, the proportion of runs where the method detected all truly different group means. The power

results presented by Ramsey et al. (2011) are averaged across the distributions considered: normal, uniform, double exponential, and exponential.

The Fan and Hancock paper (2012) provides alternatives to an omnibus ANOVA procedure with PCPs. These alternatives are based on maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) in robust means modeling (RMM) which draws on structural equation modeling. However, for more than two groups, the authors consider no sample sizes as small as 10, Moreover, Fan and Hancock consider a positively skewed but not a negatively skewed distribution. Finally, the distributions considered are unimodal rather than the normal mixtures herein examined that can be bimodal.

Parra-Frutos and Molera (2021) show that use of a transformation of the Welch (1951) test for the omnibus ANOVA procedure that corrects for both skewness and kurtosis is preferable to the usual Welch test for asymmetric heavy tailed distributions with high heteroscedasticity and is preferable to Johnson's (1978) transformation trimmed mean Welch test with normal, near normal, and light tailed distributions. Unlike our simulation design, the skewness they consider is always non-negative and sample sizes are at least 15.

Stehlik, et. al. (2024) analyze environmental contamination data that are non-normal with unequal variance using the Fisher-Behren's two sample t-test test with and without outliers. They introduce a sampling technique that orders the data and determine how many of the upper quantiles of the data can be added to the lower set while keeping the Wilks-Shapiro test insignificant. The samples considered in their paper are all larger than 60.

Background

Let us consider some characteristics of the probability mass function of certain normal mixtures, X :

$$f(X) = pf_a(X) + (1-p)f_b(X), \quad (1)$$

where p is the mixing proportion and $f_a(X)$ and $f_b(X)$ are normal distributions and standard deviations of (μ_a, σ_a) and (μ_b, σ_b) , respectively. This paper considers the case where $\sigma_a = \sigma_b = \sigma$. A wide range of skewness and kurtosis for a normal mixture can occur when varying the values of p , σ , and μ_a . Note μ_b is determined by p , μ_a , and the required mean of the normal mixture. The exact distribution of the one sample t test for a normal mixture is presented by Lee and Gurland (1977), and the two sample t test is considered by Lee and D'Agostino (1976). Cohen (1967) presents a simplified procedure for dissecting a normal mixture using the method of moments and assuming equal variance in the two mixed distributions. Subrahmaniam et al. (1975) examine the robustness of ANOVA when sampling from a normal mixture. Mendell et al. (1991) provide an estimate of the alternative distribution of the likelihood ratio test for two-component mixtures when the components have different means but equal variances.

Consider the usual one-way fixed-effects, ANOVA model:

$$X_{ij} = \mu_i + \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad i = 1, \dots, k \text{ and } j = 1, \dots, n_i, \quad (2)$$

where X_{ij} is the j^{th} observation from the i^{th} population from the normal mixture with mean μ_j with standard deviation σ_i . The ε_{ij} are independent and from a normal mixture with parameters (p, σ, μ_a) . We are concerned with the performance of procedures that are protected by an omnibus test of the hypothesis that all means are equal prior to testing all pairwise comparisons of the k individual means as well as procedures that are unprotected. The confidence interval of the comparison to be studied is

$$\bar{X}_i - \bar{X}_{i'} \pm q_{v_1, v_2, \alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{n_i} + \frac{1}{n_{i'}} \right)} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{X}_i and $\bar{X}_{i'}$ are sample means from random samples with $n_i = n_{i'} = n$ from populations i and i' respectively; q is a quantile from the Tukey HSD distribution with degrees of freedom v_1 and v_2 , α is the probability needed for $1 - \alpha$ simultaneous coverage of the interval; and $\hat{\sigma}^2$ is the pooled variance estimate. Specific values of v_1 , v_2 and σ^2 will be discussed below. Although data adjustments, such as trimmed means, are one of the most prevalent ways of handling outliers that create non-normality or unequal variance, as justified by Ramsey et al. (2011), we are testing comparisons of population means and not trimmed means. We are not considering procedures that would eliminate the characteristics of a normal mixture as it obscures the underlying issue of misspecified models. Also, in this paper we do not consider transformations of the response variable, X , because of the difficulties of interpreting the resulting confidence interval in the context of the original problem.

Simulation

Various studies have shown that the performance of PCPs is insensitive to the number of groups, most recently including the paper of Koca et al. (2013) with respect to FDR. Thus, the simulation herein is for comparisons of four group means but should be relevant for current applications that involve many more groups.

Simulation Settings

Table 1 summarizes the $((7+4) \times 6 \times 3 \times 2)$ design of our simulation. The simulation design has seven normal mixture distributions. In each of the normal mixtures $\sigma_a = \sigma_b = 1$, In addition, for the four skewed normal mixtures, both positive and negative skewness is considered. The following settings use the design of Ramsey et al. (2011). In addition to the $(7+4)$ normal mixtures, there are six effect sizes, three sample sizes and two configurations of means. The seven normal mixtures are described in Table 1. The Cohen effect sizes are 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2 and

2.5 evenly distributed over the approximate range of effect sizes in Ramsey et al. (2011). The restatement of Cohen's effect size, ϕ , for the unequal variance case by Ramsey et al. (2010) becomes:

$$\phi = \sqrt{\frac{k(k-1)\Delta}{(k(k-2)\Delta+1)} \frac{n}{(n-1)} \frac{\sum(\mu_i - \mu)^2}{\sum\sigma_i^2}}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\Delta = \frac{\sum\sigma_i^4}{(\sum\sigma_i^2)^2}. \quad (5)$$

These effect sizes are determined by setting values of the four population means. The two configurations of four population means ($\mu_1, \mu_2, \mu_3, \mu_4$) are one extreme mean (OEM) where $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = 0, \mu_4 = r$ where

$$r = \frac{\phi}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\sum\sigma_i^2} \frac{k(k-1)\Delta}{(k(k-2)\Delta+1)} \frac{n(k-1)}{(n-1)k}} \right)} \quad (6)$$

and two extreme means (TEM) where $\mu_1 = -r, \mu_2 = \mu_3 = 0, \mu_4 = r$ with r in this case defined by:

$$r = \frac{\phi}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\sum\sigma_i^2} \frac{k(k-1)\Delta}{(k(k-2)\Delta+1)} \frac{n}{(n-1)}} \right)}. \quad (7)$$

We choose the values of r to obtain the desired effect sizes. The population variances match those in Dunnett (1980) and Ramsey et al. (2011) with the four population variances of the form 1, c, c^2 and c^3 where $c = 1, 1.6, \text{ and } 2$. The three parameters in (1) for each of the four normal mixtures $p, \mu_a,$ and σ are selected so that the distribution of X has the mean and variance that satisfy the required configurations above. Note that in the case of Mixture #1 where $p = 1$ and $c = 1$, each of the four groups has a normal distribution with variance, $c=1$. Mixtures #2 and

#3 are symmetric and bimodal with differences in kurtosis. Mixtures #4 and #5 are moderately skewed with differences in kurtosis. Mixtures #6 and #7 are strongly skewed. Mixture #7 is the exceptional case where HFF is not robust, i.e., extreme heteroscedasticity and maximized difference in skewness and kurtosis among the populations.

The mixture proportions that give nonzero skewness are 0.2 and 0.058824. With those values and $r > 0$, μ_a is to the left of μ_b , and the normal mixture is negatively skewed. To obtain positive skewness, change the sign of the population deviations, $(X_{ij} - \mu_i)$, of the sampled values for the negatively skewed distributions and add the deviations to their population means resulting in μ_a being to the right of μ_b .

The simulation of 500,000 runs using the design and settings in Table 1 was initially conducted in Visual Basic 6 and reproduced in Excel Visual Basic for Applications (Eakin, 2023).

[Insert Table 1 here]

For each setting of the simulation, we compare two PCPs. The first is the Ramsey HFF, found by Ramsey (2011) to be a robust and effective alternative to slightly more powerful but considerably more complex procedures. HFF is an ordinary ANOVA F test followed by the Hayter-Fisher adaptation of Tukey's HSD:

$$W_{v,1-\alpha} = q_{k-1,n-k} \quad (8)$$

The second PCP is our unique adaptation that adjusts for unequal variance, designated the EHF. This adaptation starts with the Brown-Forsythe F test using Mehrotra's (1997) modified F degrees of freedom, v_1 and v_2 , which for equal sample sizes are

$$v_1 = \frac{[k - 1]^2}{(k(k - 2)) \frac{\sum s_i^4}{(\sum s_i^2)^2} + 1} \quad (9)$$

and

$$v_2 = (n_g - 1) \frac{(\sum s_i^2)^2}{\sum s_i^4} \quad (10)$$

where s_i^2 is the i^{th} sample variance and n_g is the common sample size. In equation (3), $\hat{\sigma}^2$ symbolizes both the pooled variance estimate in the regular HFF and the Brown-Forsythe variance estimate in EHF.

Tomarken and Serlin (1986) found the Brown-Forsythe F test robust for sample sizes less than 6. This F test is then followed by Tukey’s HSD statistic using the Games-Howell adjustment of denominator degrees of freedom in (10) combined with the Hayter-Fisher adjustment of numerator degrees of freedom in (8). Games-Howell has been shown to control Type I errors under assumption violations and has slightly more power than other procedures to which it was compared (Sauder & DeMars, 2019). The Hayter-Fisher procedure is often recommended as a more powerful procedure than Tukey’s original HSD (Richter & McCann, 2012).

In addition, we look at procedures without an initial protective omnibus F test. The HFF and EHF procedures defined previously are referred to as protected procedures. For the unprotected or “full” case standard procedure, we use Tukey’s HSD but without an initial ANOVA F test. For the unprotected or “full” case adjusted procedure we use Tukey’s HSD with the Games-Howell adjustments but without the initial Brown-Forsythe test. Thus, we have four distinct cases: the standard full procedure using Tukey’s HSD alone, the adjusted full procedure controlling for unequal variances using the Games-Howell adjustments of Tukey’s HSD, the standard protected procedure that adds an initial ANOVA F and the variance adjusted protected

procedure controlling for nonnormality and outliers with an initial Brown-Forsythe F test. Each of these procedures is observed for both positively skewed and negatively skewed distributions, designated as “Standard Approach: Full +, Full -, Prot +, Prot - and Adjusted Approach for Assumption Violations: Full +, Full -, Prot +, Prot -.

Metrics

The metrics for comparing performances are (a) COVERAGE (Dodge, 2003), average across runs of the proportion of the 95% simultaneous confidence interval estimates containing the true pairwise differences in means; (b) FWER (Tukey J. W., 1953), the family-wise error rate, previously defined as the probability of at least one Type I error among all pairwise comparisons; (c) SIGNIFICANCE OF OMNIBUS, proportion of runs where the initial omnibus F test rejected the null of all means equal; (d) ANY-PAIR POWER (Ramsey P. H., 1978), previously defined as the proportion of runs where the procedure detected at least one true difference in means; (e) ALL-PAIRS POWER (Ramsey P. H., 1978), previously defined as the proportion of runs where the method detected all truly different group means; (f) AVERAGE TYPE I ERROR RATE, average across runs of the proportion of Type I errors given all comparisons; and (g) FALSE DISCOVERY RATE (FDR) (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995), previously defined as the average proportion of Type I errors given all significant differences.

Simulation results

With respect to our original objectives, we successfully replicate a portion of Ramsey’s (2011) simulation for distributions of normal mixtures and find HFF to be similarly robust and powerful. Overall, our novel procedure, EHF, whether full or protected, was not an improvement on Ramsey’s HFF procedure with respect to either robustness or power although performances are not dissimilar. However, in this simulation we observe a surprising and interesting pattern

when comparing performance metrics for positively skewed distributions to those for negatively skewed distributions with both protected and full procedures. Tables that follow report power and robustness for all mixtures and metrics under HFF and the unprotected cases. We briefly summarize selected cases comparing HFF to EHF and then discuss in detail the impact of skewness on power and the comparison of HFF to EHF for our mixture #7 that exhibits the most extreme violation of assumption. All cases (396) with 7 metrics are available upon request.

In what follows we compare HFF to EHF for selected normal mixture distributions using FWER as the metric for robustness and ALL-PAIRS POWER as the metric for power. Specifically, for distribution normal #1, where $c = 1$, i.e., variances are equal, HFF protected is slightly more powerful than EHF or even HFF full. The observed FWER alpha is 0.05 for HFF and EHF. For mixture # 3 with bimodal symmetry, $c = 2$, i.e., unequal variance, HFF protected is more powerful than the full or protected EHF. The observed alphas for FWER for both full procedures are .08 and .10. respectively. For mixture #5 with moderate skewness, we see a difference in power between positively and negatively skewed distributions. Again, HFF has slightly smaller observed Type 1 error, .09 vs .12, and slightly more power than EFF. As before, power is better for protected procedures and FWER is smaller for full procedures. For mixture #7 we observe a similar pattern. Table 2 provides robustness metrics.

[Insert Table 2 here]

For all cases, both HFF and EHF procedures are more powerful for the OEM configuration of means than for the TEM configuration. In summary, adjusting for unequal variance or nonnormality with EHF does not seem to increase Type I error substantially nor improve the power of the HFF procedure. We discuss the interesting difference between positive and negative skewness for the power of HFF that our simulation design reveals with the OEM

configuration of means before comparing the results of HFF, EHF, and the two full procedures: HSD and HSD with Games-Howell.

This surprising pattern reflects what we see in Figure 2 for the observed SIGNIFICANCE OF OMNIBUS F test. Figure 2 is based on the ANOVA F test for the simulation where $c = 2$, $p = (1/17)$, $n = 5$, and OEM, i.e., small sample sizes, extreme heteroscedasticity, and maximized difference in skewness and kurtosis among the populations. For the smallest effect size of 0.5, the F test is more powerful for negatively skewed distributions (Wageman & Baker, 1997) than for positively skewed distributions, but this pattern reverses for all larger values of effect sizes.

[Insert Figure 2 here]

Why we see this intersection of the simulated power curves is explained by Figure 3 which illustrates the correlation between the numerator, MST, and the denominator, MSE, of the ANOVA F when distributions are skewed. Figures 3a and 3c are for positively skewed distributions and indicate the resulting positive correlations between MST and MSE, whereas Figures 3b and 3d are for negatively skewed distributions with a corresponding negative correlation between numerator and denominator. The line represents the distinction between significant results at the 0.05 level; significant cases are shown above the line, and cases that are not significant are shown below the line. Figures 3a and 3b are for the smallest effect size of 0.5, whereas Figures 3c and 3d are for moderately large effect sizes of 1.5. Because this line of distinction always slopes upward, when the correlation between MST and MSE is positive, a large portion of their joint distribution tends to rise above the line of distinction when effect size increases from 0.5 to 1.5. However, when the correlation between MST and MSE is negative (i.e., for negatively skewed distributions) increases in MSE are not accompanied by commensurate increases in MST, so the joint distribution of MST and MSE rises at a slower rate

above the line of distinction with an increase in effect size. The initial power advantage for negatively skewed distributions for the smallest effect size is quickly reversed.

[Insert Figure 3 here]

The clustering and angle of the points in Figure 3 are a result of the combined effects of the bimodal nature of normal mixtures, skewed distributions, and the OEM configuration of population means in which the one extreme mean is to the right of the other three. As mentioned before, for our design, μ_a is to the left of μ_b for negatively skewed normal mixture distributions and μ_a is to the right of μ_b for positively skewed distributions. The primary modes (μ_a) of the normal mixtures for the second and third distributions are to the left of the single normal mean. See Figures 4a – 4d. The primary mode for the normal mixture of the fourth distribution, the one with a different mean, is to the right of the single normal mean. In other words, the primary mode of the fourth distribution moves in an opposite direction from the single normal mean than the primary modes of the second and third distributions. Whereas for negatively skewed distributions the primary modes are to the right of the single normal mean for all three of the remaining distributions. Thus, for small effect sizes with positively skewed distributions, the one extreme mean (r) will be relatively near the secondary modes (μ_b) and difficult to detect, statistically. This results in decreased power for the F test with positively skewed distributions relative to negatively skewed distributions. As the effect size increases, the extreme mean moves beyond the secondary modes and the power of the F test with positively skewed distributions will surpass that for negatively skewed distributions. For one extreme mean to the left, instead of the right, the distributions appear as a mirror image of Figures 4a-4d.

[Insert Figure 4 here]

We first examine the HFF procedure. For the full case HFF reverts to HSD, and the metrics are always calculated as the proportion of the 500,000 simulation runs. However, for the protected cases with HFF, the metrics can be calculated one of two ways: (1) as the proportion of total simulation runs or (2) as the proportion of runs for which the omnibus F test is significant. For Figures 5 – 9, the sub-figures denoted as (a) display the unconditional empirical probability with the divisor of 500,000. The sub-figures denoted as (b) display the conditional empirical probability given that the protective omnibus F test is significant. Thus, sub-figures (a) and (b) that follow provide a visual comparison of the unconditional and conditional observed proportions respectively for full and protected procedures with positively and negatively skewed normal mixture distributions with small sample sizes, one extreme mean, extreme heteroscedasticity, and maximized difference in skewness and kurtosis among the populations. Figures 5-9 depict results for only the standard cases HFF (protected) and HSD (full) with positive and negative skewness in the normal mixture. The procedures that adjust for unequal variances, EHF (protected) and HSD with Games Howell (full) are less powerful than the standard cases which are robust with empirical Type I error metrics no more than approximately 1.5 alpha.

Figures 5a and 5b display the COVERAGE metric. Theoretically, confidence interval COVERAGE for all pairwise differences in means should not depend on the effect size. This is shown in Figure 5a for the full procedures and in Figure 5b for both full and protected procedures where COVERAGE is nearly identical and almost constant for positively and negatively skewed normal mixtures. However, for the protected procedures in Figure 5b, the HSD is only applied when simulated cases are above the line of significance in Figure 3. Thus, for the smallest effect sizes there are more cases that meet this threshold from negatively skewed

distributions than from positively skewed distributions, but this pattern quickly reverses as the relative power of the F test changes with increases in effect size. With fewer cases, and these with more extreme differences between sample and population means in negatively skewed distributions than in positively skewed distributions, COVERAGE will not be as good, reflecting the pattern we saw for SIGNIFICANCE OF OMNIBUS in Figure 2.

[Insert Figure 5 here]

The power of the F test should be correlated with the ANY-PAIR POWER metric for Tukey's HSD procedure since both are looking for just one significant difference in means. This is shown in Figure 6a where the only real differences among the four cases are observed between the positively and negatively skewed distributions. One might expect the full procedure to have greater power than the procedure protected by an omnibus F test just because it is applied more often. However, the Hayter-Fisher adaptation which changes the numerator degrees of freedom of Tukey's HSD compensates for this anticipated loss of power. This is shown in Figure 6b for the two full lines. However, in the protected case, the F test has already rejected the null hypothesis, so the power of the Tukey procedure should be almost one. This is shown in the two protected lines in Figure 6b.

[Insert Figure 6 here]

Consider ALL-PAIRS POWER for the protected procedure with unconditional probabilities in Figure 7a. For a given run, the metric is recorded as the value one if all non-zero pairwise differences are detected, not just a single difference; and the metric is a zero otherwise. Thus, for the unconditional probabilities, ALL-PAIRS POWER is less than ANY-PAIR POWER. ALL-PAIRS POWER in Figure 7a shows a difference between positively skewed and negatively skewed distributions that reflects the pattern we have seen for the F test and for ANY-

PAIR POWER. Given the skewness of the distribution, i.e., positively or negatively skewed, the protected procedure has slightly more power than the full procedure due to the smaller size of the critical values from the decrease in the numerator degrees of freedom. Looking at Figure 7b, the conditional probabilities are greater for the protected than the full procedures with some crossing still observed that results from the correlation of MST and MSE.

[Insert Figure 7 here]

The results for unconditional ALL-PAIRS POWER are summarized in Table 3. Note that the designation of moderate skewness indicates a maximum skewness coefficient among the four groups of 1.2; strong skewness indicates a maximum skewness coefficient of 3.1. When comparing the full to the protected procedures with unconditional metrics there is a 2.5 percentage point increase in FWER as shown in Figure 8a. However, the increase in FWER is off-set by increases in both ANY-PAIR POWER and ALL PAIRS POWER and FWER is still at the 0.05 significance level (which would be expected with a normal distribution but not necessarily a normal mixture). Thus, the protected procedures are preferable to the full for this case. With the conditional FWER metric we see the inverse of the pattern for COVERAGE and ANY-PAIR POWER which mirrors the explanation above for Figures 4b and 5b, respectively. A similar discussion would hold for the AVERAGE TYPE I ERROR RATE.

[Insert Table 3 here]

[Insert Figure 8 here]

The FDR is equivalent to the number of incorrect rejections divided by the sum of the number of correct and incorrect rejections. For the unconditional FDR in Figure 9a, we see a pattern like FWER in Figure 7a but with greater impact of skewness for the smallest effect size. In all cases, however, the FDR is less than $\alpha/2$. For the conditional FDR in Figure 9b, we again

see a pattern like FWER with a magnified effect of skewness for the smallest effect size. Thus, in looking at multiple metrics for the case of small sample sizes, one extreme mean, extreme heteroscedasticity, and maximized difference in skewness and kurtosis among the populations, we see the relationship to the power of the F test. This power in turn changes with changes in the correlation of the numerator and denominator of the F test statistic. We observe the first four moments influence correlation but do not completely determine power, which also depends upon higher moments of the normal mixtures (Lee & Gurland, 1977). With everything else held constant, if the skewness changes sign, we observe a strong change in power resulting from the changed correlation between the MST and MSE.

[Insert Figure 9 here]

Returning to comparison of HFF and EHF for other cases in the simulation, when protected and unprotected by an omnibus procedure, we will discuss the results for ALL-PAIRS POWER. For the case of symmetric normal mixtures with homogeneity, the full HFF and EHF procedures are slightly less powerful than the protected procedures. For moderately skewed (whether positively or negatively, $p = 1/5$) normal mixtures with extreme heterogeneity ($c = 2$), both HFF and EHF tend to be more powerful with negatively skewed distributions than with positively skewed distributions for smaller effect sizes, but then this pattern changes for larger effect sizes similar to the crossing of the power curves discussed earlier. Finally, for normal mixtures that are strongly skewed ($p = 1/17$) with extreme heterogeneity we get a crossing pattern discussed earlier. For both moderately and strongly skewed mixtures the protected cases are always more powerful than the full. In no case is EHF generally superior to HFF.

Discussion

Considering again the hypothetical example in the introduction, our simulation results show that the power of both the F test and the multiple comparison procedures differs for a normal mixture that is positively skewed (means are greater for the female only pairs) and a normal mixture that is negatively skewed (means are smaller for the female only pairs). This pattern of change in the power of both the ANOVA F and the multiple comparison procedures, resulting from changes in the correlation of MSE and MST with changes in the direction of skewness, has not been examined previously from our search of literature.

Even though our proposed procedure, EHF, does not generally improve on the HFF procedure for the normal mixtures and cases considered, this study reveals some helpful lessons for using multiple comparison procedures. When looking for small effects with normal mixtures and small sample sizes, both third and fourth moments impact the correlation of MST and MSE.

The direction of skewness dominates in the designs we considered. The metrics of power and Type I error seem to indicate that the protected procedure with the Hayter-Fisher adjustment is sufficiently robust and slightly more powerful than the unprotected procedure for most effect sizes. These results suggest that perhaps comparable results would hold for single modal distributions that cover the same ranges of skewness and kurtosis. Researchers would do well to search for procedures applicable to their data rather than to search for a generally superior procedure. Most importantly, we recommend that researchers retain outliers (at least initially) in order to examine graphic indications of model misspecification and consider the tests of J. B. Ramsey (1969) for detecting missing variables when appropriate.

Declaration of interest

Preliminary findings for a portion of the simulations were published in *Proceedings of the American Statistical Association*, Montreal, Canada, August 2013, pp. 1928-1930. We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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Table 1:
Summary of Design Parameters and Settings for the Simulations

<i>Design Parameters</i>	<i>Settings</i>
k = number of groups	k = 4
n = sample sizes, equal for all groups	n = 5, 10, 15
p = mixture weights, equal for all groups	p = 1, .5, .2, .058824
c = configuration of variance levels	c = 1, 1.6, 2 - (variances of 4 groups are 1, c, c ² , c ³)
Mixture distributions simulated	Mix #1. c=1 and p=1; Normal (not a mixture) with equal variance for all groups Mix #2. c=1.6 and p=.5; Symmetric bimodal with moderately unequal variance Mix #3. c = 2 and p =.5; Symmetric bimodal with strongly unequal variance Mix #4. c = 1.6 and p =.2; Moderately skewed with moderately unequal variance Mix #5. c = 2 and p=.2; Moderately skewed with strongly unequal variance Mix #6. c = 1.6 and p= 0.058824; Strongly skewed with moderately unequal variance Mix #7. c = 2 and p= 0.058824; Strongly skewed with strongly unequal variance
Direction of skewness,	Positive, negative - same for all groups, Mixs #4-#7
Configuration of means	One extreme mean (OEM), two extreme means (TEM) (means of the four groups are 0, 0, 0, r or -r, 0, 0, r)
Cohen effect sizes	Cohen effect sizes = 0, .5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5(r above is a function of Coen effect sizes, see equations 6, 7)
<i>Performance Metrics</i>	
General	COVERAGE
Robustness	Family Wise Error Rate (FWER) AVERAGE TYPE I ERROR RATE False Discovery Rate (FDR)
Power	SIGNIFICANCE OF OMNIBUS ANY-PAIR POWER ALL-PAIRS POWER

Table 2. Robustness Metrics * for the Full or Unprotected Case (Metrics Calculated Regardless of F Test Value) using Tukey’s HSD

<i>Single Normal Mix</i>	1					
	Sample Size	5	10	15		
Coverage	0.989	0.989	0.989			
Observed Alpha	0.050	0.050	0.050			
Avg % Type I Err	0.011	0.011	0.011			
<i>Symmetric Bimodal Mix</i>	2			3		
	Sample Size	5	10	15	5	10
Coverage	0.982	0.985	0.986	0.975	0.981	0.982
Observed Alpha	0.068	0.062	0.061	0.082	0.071	0.069
Avg % Type I Err	0.018	0.015	0.014	0.025	0.019	0.018
<i>Moderately Skewed Mix</i>	4			5		
	Sample Size	5	10	15	5	10
Coverage	0.984	0.985	0.986	0.977	0.978	0.98
Observed Alpha	0.065	0.064	0.062	0.092	0.085	0.076
Avg % Type I Err	0.016	0.015	0.014	0.023	0.022	0.020
<i>Strongly Skewed Mix</i>	6			7		
	Sample Size	5	10	15	5	10
Coverage	0.988	0.987	0.986	0.984	0.981	0.979
Observed Alpha	0.052	0.060	0.063	0.066	0.084	0.091
Avg % Type I Err	0.012	0.013	0.014	0.016	0.019	0.021

*Notes:

1. Any-Pair and All-Pair power are not applicable under the null hypothesis.
2. Case 1-3 are for symmetric distributions; no separate positive and negative situations.
3. Given the sample size and case, the absolute value of differences in robustness are
 - (a) less than 0.001 between all positive and negative skewness situations and
 - (b) less than 0.002 between Observed Alpha, Exp Error Rate and FDR.
4. Moderately skewed means the maximum skewness of the four populations is less than 1.2 while strongly skewed means less than 3.1

PAIRWISE COMPARISONS FOR SMALL SAMPLES

Table 3: Comparison of Unconditional All-PAIR POWER, OEM, Sample Size = 5

Effect*	<i>Standard Approach=HFF</i>				<i>Adjusted Approach for Violations = EHF</i>			
	Full-	Full+	Prot-	Prot+	Full-	Full+	Prot-	Prot+
<i>a. Symmetric Distributions</i>								
0.5	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03
1	0.45	0.45	0.55	0.55	0.25	0.25	0.37	0.37
1.5	0.93	0.93	0.96	0.96	0.77	0.77	0.87	0.87
2	1	1	1	1	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99
2.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
<i>b. Moderately Skewed Distributions**</i>								
0.5	0.19	0.04	0.24	0.07	0.12	0	0.17	0.01
1	0.44	0.41	0.51	0.53	0.31	0.08	0.34	0.14
1.5	0.79	0.93	0.84	0.96	0.47	0.47	0.58	0.66
2	0.97	1	0.98	1	0.74	0.91	0.82	0.97
2.5	1	1	1	1	0.92	1	0.97	1
<i>c. Strongly Skewed Distributions**</i>								
0.5	0.27	0.06	0.34	0.09	0.17	0.02	0.25	0.04
1	0.68	0.57	0.71	0.65	0.58	0.35	0.65	0.4
1.5	0.74	0.89	0.75	0.93	0.72	0.51	0.73	0.56
2	0.88	0.99	0.93	0.99	0.74	0.7	0.74	0.84
2.5	0.97	1	0.98	1	0.75	0.94	0.79	0.98

Notes: * Full indicates metrics are calculated regardless of F test Significance,

Prot indicates metrics are calculated only if F test is Significant

+ and – indicate the correlation between MSR and MSE

** Moderately and Strongly skewed are defined in Table 2

Figure 1

a. Normal mixture of the populations

b. Comparison of population means

Figure 2

Figure 3

a. Positive skewness, effect size = 0.5, power = 0.3, correlation = 0.73

b. Negative skewness, effect size = 0.5, power = 0.6, correlation = -0.30

c. Positive skewness, effect size = 1.5, power = 1, correlation = 0.72

d. Negative skewness, Effect size = 1.5, power = 0.8, correlation = -0.61

Note: The shading of the points corresponds to the percentage of the simulation runs which have the indicated coordinates for MST and MSE values. The legend shows the partition of the percentages.

Figure 4

a. Negative skewness, effect size = 0.5

b. Positive skewness, effect size = 0.5

c. Negative skewness, effect size = 2.5

d. Positive skewness, effect size = 2.5

Figure 5

a. Coverage out of 500,000

b. Coverage out of number of F rejections

Figure 6

a. Any-pair power out of 500,000

b. Any-pair power out of number of F rejections

Figure 7

a. All-pair power out of 500,000

b. All-pair power out of number of F rejections

Figure 8

a. FWER out of 500,000

b. FWER out of number of F rejections

Figure 9

a. FDR out of 500,000

b. FDR out of number of F rejections

Figure Captions

Figure 1: Comparison of normal mixtures and means of the normal populations comprising the mixture

Figure 2: Significance of the Omnibus F test. $c = 2$, $p = (1/17)$, $n = 5$, and OEM

Figure 3: Relationship between correlation and power as effect size changes

Figure 4: Normal mixtures with different skewness and effect size

Figure 5: HFF Coverage versus effect size with (protected) and without (full) initial ANOVA F:

HFF is Tukey's HSD with Hayter-Fisher approach, $c=2$, $p=1/17$, OEM and $n=5$

Figure 6: HFF Any-pair power versus effect size with (protected) and without (full) initial

ANOVA F: HFF is Tukey's HSD with Hayter-Fisher approach, $c=2$, $p=1/17$, OEM and $n=5$

Figure 7: HFF All-pair power versus effect size with (protected) and without (full) initial

ANOVA F: HFF is Tukey's HSD with Hayter-Fisher approach $c=2$, $p=1/17$, OEM and $n=5$,
OEM

Figure 8: HFF Family-wise error rate versus effect size with (protected) and without (full) initial

ANOVA F: HFF is Tukey's HSD with Hayter-Fisher approach, $c=2$, $P=1/17$, OEM and $n=5$

Figure 9: HFF False discovery rate versus effect size with (protected) and without (full) initial

ANOVA F: HFF is Tukey's HSD with Hayter-Fisher approach, $c=2$, $p=1/17$, OEM and $n=5$